

Nanostructured metal oxides as efficient photocatalytic material

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Metal oxides are considered to be promising photocatalyst because of their efficiency in generation of charge carriers on exposure of light. According to the literature, metal oxides such as TiO_2 , ZnO , CeO_2 , ZrO_2 , WO_3 , SnO_2 , and $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ are proven to be efficient catalysts in the field of photocatalysis [1],[2]. We are involved in the formation of the faceted structure of ZnO and their photocatalytic application. Faceted structures are important as the type of exposed facet have a strong influence on the catalytic activity of the nanomaterials [3]. We have synthesized faceted structures of ZnO by the decomposition of zinc oxalate in the presence of flux. Here, we have used NaCl and KCl as flux for preferential growth of (110) plane. We have observed a high value of texture coefficient for (110) plane in the presence of mixture of NaCl - KCl as flux. These faceted structures were used for the photocatalytic degradation of aqueous solution RhB dye. We observed that 53% of the degradation occurred in 70 minutes for ZnO synthesized in the absence of flux whereas ~61% and 63% of the dye was degraded when ZnO formed in presence of NaCl and KCl respectively as a flux were used as photocatalyst. Apart from this, we have carried out photocatalytic activity on various other oxides such as hollow nanostructures of ZnO , BiFeO_3 , and ZnFe_2O_4 . We have synthesized hollow ZnO spheres using PEG400 as structure directing agent and carried out its photocatalytic activity. We observed that RhB dye was degraded up to 99% in 50 min on irradiation of ultra-violet light using these hollow spheres.

Fig.1 (a) SEM images of ZnO in (a) absence of flux, Fig.2 SEM image of ZnO with (b) 1:1 mixture of NaCl - KCl . hollow structure.

References:

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